

Dynamics of electrode potential offset

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Abstract

There was proposed the method of near-electrode potential measurement by way of current interruption. To obtain experimental data, a specially designed device was used. With the help of this device, we managed to measure with sufficient accuracy the true potential of the electric double layer and the degree of its change. The measurement results are given for aqueous solutions of univalent and bivalent metal salts.

Keywords: Conductometric cell, Electrolytes, Electrode potential, Double electrical layer.

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1. Introduction

In conductometry and polarimetry, the electrode potential offset at current pass plays a big part. The near-electrode processes at current pass are complicated and sometimes, their nature is not clear. That is why in this paper, we put emphasis on experimental investigations of some potential peculiarities extremely important for comprehension of conductometers functioning and for new systems projecting of electrolyte conductivity (conductometers) [1].

As indications of a complexity of processes running in electrolyte containing electric chains, voltage-current characteristics can serve. The Faradaic component of the electrode-electrolyte contact has the non-linear voltage-current characteristic.

Figure 1. Example of dependence between electrode-electrolyte voltage-current characteristics and temperature. There are given the following characteristics: voltage – current density for the boundary layer made by the contact of Cu and the KOH solution in amount of 6.25 M. (Reproduced on [2]). Temperature: 1 – 25°C; 2 – 80°C.

The non-linearity of the voltage-current characteristics has a complicated and often non-monotonous nature. It heavily depends on electrolyte composition, electrode material and temperature. As a typical example, the voltage-current characteristics can serve of the contact Cu – KOH solution. Those characteristics have complicated structure heavily depending on temperature and concentration, Figure (1) [2]. For such characteristics, a presence is typical

of areas of negative resistance on both absolute value and negative differential resistance.

The differential conductivity of a contact layer between a conductor and an electrolyte can change from large values down to zero (in extreme points of voltage-current characteristic), Figure (1). The dependence on composition, temperature and speed of voltage variations changes the form of voltage-current characteristic so intensely and incalculably that always the probability exists of occurrence of unacceptably big error of conductivity measurement with use of two-electrode method.

In this paper experimentally, we study the dependence of electrode potential on electrolyte composition and current prehistory in a two-electrode cell.

2. Method of excessive potential measurement

The method relies heavily on observation and/or measurement of excessive potential at a current interruption moment (at “current pause”) [3]. At the current interruption moment in any points, the potential in the electrolyte is the same. Also at this moment on electrodes, an apparent difference of excessive potentials of two electrodes is observed. (In common conditions – i.e. at presence of a current in the chain, – this value is not observed.)

Figure 2. Scheme for explanation of the experimental stand principle of action. 1 – generator of impulses of heteropolar voltage; 2 – generator of impulses of current interruption; 3 – key; 4 – current-voltage converter; 5 – conductometric cell; 6 – digital oscillograph.

Notably, exactly this potential contributes mainly into a voltage measurement imprecision. Based on the proposed method, the experimental stand - Figure (2) was developed and constructed.

Into the stand, a possibility is laid down of measurement of voltage and time-related parameters of both pilot pulses and interrupting ones. In the stand, means are foreseen for simultaneous observation of current and conductometric cell with aid of a current-voltage converter.

The stand consists of the following components: a switchable generator with divisible frequency series: 61; 122; 244.1; 488.3; 976.6; 1953.1; 3906.3; 7812.5; 15625; 31250; 62500 Hz; a source of calibrated voltage pulses with zero component of average current; an electronic key of generator current-cutter with divisible times 32, 64, 128, ... microseconds synchronized with the generator; a multi-range converter of current-voltage with a band up to 4 MHz; a high-ohmic preamplifier with input resistance 1012 Ohm and frequency band 4 MHz.

The observation and registration of the resultant time-related characteristics of voltage and current is executed by a digital oscillograph ACK-3151 (digit capacity 8 bit; band 150 MHz; sensibility 10 mV/cell (0.3 mV/bit).

Quartz conductometric cells were made in the form of rectangular parallelepiped with two noncontinuous electrodes on its facets, Figure (3).

Figure 3. Photo of the experimental stand relied on the method of direct measurement of excessive electrode potential at current pass in a conductometric cell.

3. Calibration and time-related characteristics checking

The stand calibration for the measurement conduction of excessive electrode potential at current pass in the electrolytes was implemented with aid of in-line connection of a precision resistor into the chain instead of a conductometric cell.

Figure 4. Calibration of experimental stand on reference resistor. (a) – oscillograms of voltage on conductometric cell simulator (upper curve) and of current (lower curve); (b) - the same with eightfold time-based expansion.

After setting of frequency and time interval of interruption, a measurement was performed of time dependence of current and voltage at various values of the precision resistor and different current conversion efficiency.

An example of a calibrating oscillogram is given in the Figure (3). As a load, the precision resistor was used with high resistance (106 KΩ). In the Fig. 3b, the same oscillogram is given with the eightfold expansion of the selected area.

On the represented oscillogram of voltage - (Figure (3), upper curve) and of current (lower curve), it is seen clearly that – as one would expect, – cell’s potential and current at current interruption do not differ from zero.

4. Results of electrode potentials influence study

The process itself of double electrical layer charge in various time moments can be observed with aid of current interruption, too. With this purpose, on the current switch 3 (Fig. 1), series is sent of pulses controlling the interruption. On potential changes at moments of current absence, the time-based

dependence can be seen of a charge of the double electrical layer. In the Figure (6), typical results of such experiment are given (for 10% solution CaCl₂). Due to the interrupter, the curve of the potential on the conductometric cell (indigo curve) is divided onto two dashed curves. The rectangular dashed curve reflects the potential of the generator, while the curvilinear dashed curve reflects total potential of the double electrical layer on the two electrodes.

On the represented oscillograms - Figure (4), the frequency of the interruption current is the same but the frequency of pilot pulses of voltage is different. This allows seeing details of excess potential changes. At the current interruption, a potential value doesn’t stay constant (this is better seen in the Fig. 4a). This is caused by discharge of the double electrical layer capacity. Along with it, quite naturally, this current discharge depends on potential value of this capacity. As a rule, the process of re-charging of the double electrical layer capacity is close to an exponential law; although sometimes at certain concentrations in the characteristics, a rectangular area occurs.

a

b

Figure 5. Voltage oscillograms on a conductometric cell, with aqueous solutions of CaCl₂ in the concentration 10% (upper indigo curve) and of current (lower red curve) at the current interruption with the frequency 31.25 KHz. The frequency of voltage pilot pulses is 1.953 KHz (*a*) and 0.977 KHz (*b*) respectively. The isolated chaotic points are traces of transitional processes at interrupter switching-over.

This can be explained with the non-linearity of the double electrical layer capacity, which is minimal at zero voltage [4].

Another important conclusion, which is possible to be made as a result of the direct observation of time-based dependence of the potential of the double electric layer, consists in the asymptotic approximation of the potential to the final value δ , Figure (4). This value is determined by a resistance divider formed by the resistance. With a concentration growth, the resistance R_x decreases. Besides, at constant capacity and resistance of the double electrical layer $\frac{1}{2}C_{DEL}$ and $2R_{DEL}$, a speed of charge of the double electrical layer grows. If we have a certain value of R_x , the knowledge of the upside potential δ allows finding the value

$$R_{EDL} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta}{2u - \delta} R_x,$$

where u is amplitude of generator voltage.

Figure 6. Dependence of excessive potential of electrodes of a conductometric cell on concentration of aqueous KCl solution. Temperature is 24°C; frequency of pilot voltage pulses is 1.953 KHz. On the upper insertion, the same data are represented by the linear graph.

The fall of a current of the conductometric cell and the occurrence of residual voltage are going on with a concentration growth. The measurement series were conducted with determination of full dynamic characteristics by the method of the “current pause” for various concentrations of the most interested

aqueous resources from the point of view of monitoring. The same measurement series are represented in the graphic form in the Figures (6 – 9).

Figure 7. Dependence of maximum current decrease of a conductometric cell on concentration of aqueous KCl solution. The data were obtained at simultaneous measurement of dependence of excessive electrode potential represented in the Fig. 4. In the insertion above, the same data are given on the linear graph.

Figure 8. Dependence of excessive electrode potential of a conductometric cell on concentration of aqueous CaCl₂ solution. Temperature is 24 °C; frequency of voltage pilot pulses is 1.953 KHz. On the insertion above, the same data are given on the linear graph.

Figure 9. Dependence of maximum current decrease of a conductometric cell on concentration of aqueous CaCl₂ solution. The data were obtained at simultaneous measurement of dependence of excessive electrode potential represented in the Figure (7). On the insertion above, the same data are given on the linear graph.

The measurements were conducted with changing of concentration: there was applied two-fold dilution and two-and-half-fold dilution. That is why at the data graphic representation, the semilogarithmic net was used. However, it is natural to estimate the dependence linearity of the measured concentration values on the linear scale shown in the upper insertion on each figure.

Even a cursory examination of the results shows that an acceptable precision can be reached only at very small concentrations.

Let us notice that the dependence of the electrode potential of a conductometric cell on a concentration of aqueous KCl solution differs sharply of the same dependence obtained for the CaCl₂ solution. While in the first case, the dependence is almost linear - see the insertion in the Figure (5), the dependence for the CaCl₂ solution features with pronounced non-linearity - see the insertion in the Figure (9). Notably, in the area of small concentrations, the sharp increase of the electrode potential is observed. Such apparent difference between the characteristics and the chemical composition makes a calibration (with aid of standard solutions) of two-electrode conductometers justifiable. This is because it is

impossible to adapt results of a calibration with one solution (for example, KCl) to a voluntary taken solution of another composition, even in the case that this composition is known.

5. Conclusions

Thus, the investigation of boundary-related phenomena at current pass showed the necessity of a circumspective approach to measurements of solutions conductivity with aid of two-electrode conductometric cells.

The proposed method of the electrode potential direct examination proved its applicability for conductometer imprecision source finding out, their values assessment and dynamics observation of double electrical layer capacity charge.

References

- [1] V. A. Kuzmichova, "Conductometry as a basic method of continuous control of liquid media salinity", Collected book "Materials of XXV scientific-practical conference of Moscow State Academy of Aqueous Transport, Moscow, Publishing House "Altair", **2003**, pp. 55-57.
- [2] B. P. Nikolsky, "Chemist's reference book". Under editorship of B. P. Nikolsky, vol.3. Moscow, Leningrad, Publishing House "Goskhim-Izdat", **1965**, 1005 pages.
- [3] V. A. Kuzmichova, V. B. Morozov, "Direct estimation of electrode potential at current pass in conductometric cells", Moscow, Publishing House "Rechnoy Transport", **2005**, No.2. p. 58-61.
- [4] L. I. Andropov, "Theoretical electrochemistry", Moscow, Publishing House "Vysshaya shkola", **1984**, 4th edition, 509 pages.
- [5] M. Nakamura et al., "Outer Helmholtz Plane of the Electrical Double Layer Formed at the Solid Electrode-Liquid Interface" ChemPhysChem, **12** (2011) 1430.
- [6] R. A. Marcus, "Nobel Lecture: Electron Transfer Reactions in Chemistry: Theory and Experiment", [Nobel Lectures, Chemistry 1991-1995](#), Editor Bo G. Malmström, World Scientific Publishing Co., Singapore, 1997 December 8, **1992**.